

SOCLIMPACT

**Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways
in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market
evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond**

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Work Package 3:

Climate change vulnerability assessment framework and complex impact chains

Deliverable 3.1. Validated Matrix on Blue Economy sectors lead, boundaries, and statistical codes, per island focal point.

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Coastal and Maritime Tourism

Aquaculture

Marine Energy

Maritime transport

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1. Introduction

1.1. A conceptual framework of Soclimpact

Within Soclimpact, WP3 can be considered as a “scoping” work package, setting project boundaries, defining the priority impacts to be dealt with, and above all organising the interdisciplinary work and cross-work packages activities, so as to work towards a common goal. This is why all partners are involved in WP3, which requires a strong coordination (initial meeting at KO, plus two physical workshops, in Corsica (May 2018) and Roma (October 2018) and several on-line meetings. This also allows to get to know each another and enhance coordination.

Thus, the project's workflow includes a preliminary step (**WP3**), in which potential impact chains, as well as the list of needed climate and economic datasets are defined. This first deliverable is a scoping of sectors' definitions, boundaries and options chosen within the Soclimpact project. **The aim is to achieve a homogeneous and comparable treatment of Blue Economy sectors in all the European islands concerned by Soclimpact**, leading to a complete homogenization of the treatment of the Blue Economy by the accounting systems of all Islands and coastal areas of the EU.

This clear definition of project boundaries is rendered necessary by the subsequent modelling activities in WP4, WP5 and WP6, which need rigor, consistency and coordinated approaches.

1.2. Why does Soclimpact focus on Blue Economy sectors?

Blue Growth is a long-term EU strategy that supports sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors. Indeed, seas and oceans are drivers for the European economy and have great potential for innovation, jobs and growth. The strategy also aims at removing those barriers and market and non-market failures that constrain innovation and investment in the marine-maritime context. Under this approach, the European Commission initiated several successful facilitating or 'enabling' actions. Despite the advances, further growth is possible in several areas which are highlighted within the strategy.

The strategy focuses on five main blue economy sectors:

- **Aquaculture**
- **Coastal and Maritime tourism**
- Marine biotechnology
- **Renewable energy**
- Mineral resources

and highlights the relevance of other blue sectors for more value and jobs:

- **Maritime transport**
- Fisheries
- Shipbuilding and repair
- Offshore Oil & Gas

The creation of a European islands network and of a common Blue Growth framework to work on the adaptation to Climate Change (CC), not only provides evidence-based information to facilitate decision-making processes at a regional level, but also generates scientific feedback to complement and nourish actual projections for Europe. The islands participating in Soclimpact come from several sea basins:

- Atlantic Ocean
- Mediterranean Sea
- Baltic Sea
- North Sea
- Other outermost Regions (Caribbean)

Islands are vulnerable territories and many risks can damage islands, which are fragile territories in the face of climatic hazards. In the Soclimpact project, risks are defined as the interaction of vulnerability, exposure and hazard (GIZ, 2017). The sectorial composition of islands allows us to understand the complex relations of some relevant Blue Economy activities, and many key sustainability research areas, like Environmental quality, water consumption, waste management, governance structures, renewable energy sources, economic development and wealth inequality. For this reason, islands and archipelagos are considered as optimal climate change labs to generate in depth studies on Blue Economy sectors with relatively easy replicability potential to mainland. Moreover, European islands are very diverse, and need very different mitigation/adaptation packages, which contribute to enrich their replicability.

Soclimpact project focuses on four blue economy sectors: Coastal and Maritime Tourism, Aquaculture, Maritime Transport and Marine Energy. This sectoral choice has several reasons :

- a need to limit a too broad field;
- a need to define sectors a) potentially impacted by climate change (which for instance excludes mineral resources and to a lesser extent shipbuilding and repair), and b) where some already available knowledge can be mobilised (this excludes Fisheries, where the relationship between climate change and fish stocks would be a project in itself).
- the need to fit with the consortium capabilities. In particular the Soclimpact consortium includes several research centres (ULPGC, UNIBO, TEC...) and boundary organizations (OTIE...) specialised on tourism.

1.3. Outline

This first deliverable is a thematic and cross-cutting synthesis to define the four Soclimpact sectors of Blue Economy as well as their statistical boundaries. Secondly, the main impacts of climate change are analysed for each sector, so as start the brainstorming which will be detailed in the next deliverables on the impacts chains (3.2, 3.3 and 3.4.). Finally, the governance of the WP3 is presented in the form of matrices and tables to summarize the involvement of the Soclimpact partners on the 12 islands of the project.

The collected information is the result of several meetings between the partners:

- A brainstorming during the Kick-Off meeting (end of January) about climate change possible impacts per geographical scales (pilot sites, islands, regional area, *etc.*) and per sector.

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- Contributions from the sector leaders of the project: ULPGC for Coastal and Maritime Tourism, CETECIMA for Maritime Transport, ITC for Marine Energy and AquaBioTech Group for Aquaculture
- Contributions from the sector teams during online meetings
- WP3 online meetings
- WP3 meeting in Corsica: the need to meet partners physically one more time caused delays for the submission of the deliverable.

2. The definitions of sectors within the Soclimpact project

In this first section, the aim is to define and delimitate the boundaries for the 4 sectors.

2.1. Legal, statistical definitions and boundaries

In this first part, the aim is to outline the legal definitions issued in official EU documents, as well as statistical and operational definitions for each Blue economy sector studied in Soclimpact. The objective is to reconcile this various approaches, and find a practical definition and set boundaries for the rest of the project.

Table 1: Legal and statistical definitions and boundaries

	<p>COASTAL AND MARITIME TOURISM</p>
<p><i>Context</i></p> <p>“Coastal and maritime tourism is the largest maritime activity in Europe and employs almost 3.2 million people, generating a total of €183 billion in gross value added. It represents over one third of the maritime economy”.</p> <p>In islands, tourism is usually the main economic activity, not only in Europe but also around the world (Baldacchino, 2016). According to data from the World Bank (2014), 9 of the 10 countries most dependent on tourism in terms of tourism income as a percentage of GDP are islands.</p> <p><i>Definition</i></p> <p>At the 1991 UNWTO Ottawa Conference on Travel and Tourism Statistics, tourism was defined as the activities of persons traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes.</p> <p>This demand side definition basically relays on the fact that tourism is what tourists do. The REGULATION (EU) No 692/2011 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of July, 6th 2011 concerning European statistics on tourism, and repealing the Council Directive 95/57/EC also adopts a definition inspired in Ottawa’s regulation: “the activity of visitors taking a trip to a main destination outside their usual environment, for less than a year, for any main purpose, including business, leisure or other personal purpose, other than to be employed by a resident entity in the place visited.”</p> <p>The EU’s tourism statistical system relays on three methodological pillars such as the “International Recommendations for Tourism Statistics” (IRTS 2008), the “Statistics and Tourism Satellite Account Programme” (TSA 2008) and the “Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community” (NACE Rev.2–2008). In this regard, the Regulation 692/2011 updates some definitions to properly adapt the European statistical systems to the changes experimented by tourism agents and relations, and to continue providing a harmonized tourism statistics framework for the whole EU.</p> <p>More recently, EUROSTAT has come to unify different sources of prescriptions for tourism in a methodological manual for tourism statistics. It provides a rigorous definition of territorial</p>	

(NUTs), sectoral (NACE Rev.2¹) and tourism performance concepts (based on IRTS 2008 and TSA 2008) that allow for an accurate delimitation of tourism activity either for analyzing climate change impacts or evaluating those impacts on both the tourism system and the economic systems. IRTS 2008 provides a comprehensive methodological framework for collection and compilation of tourism statistics in all countries irrespective of the level of development of their statistical systems.

Based on these recommendations, countries are encouraged to develop their tourism statistics according to the following guidelines:

- Estimates should be based on reliable statistical sources, where visitors and producers of goods and services are both observed;
- Observations should be statistical in character and produced on an ongoing basis, combining the compilation of benchmark estimations with the use of indicators to enhance the usefulness of the results;
- Data should be comparable over time within the same country, comparable among countries and comparable with other fields of economic activities;
- Data should be internally consistent and presented within macroeconomic frameworks recognized at the international level.

Soclimpact assumptions

Finally, for Soclimpact purposes, it is assumed that the whole tourism activity of the islands is assigned to the coastal and maritime tourism sector (hereafter referred as tourism). It is fully justified because most of the tourist activities in islands are based on the infrastructures and the natural attractions that are distributed throughout the coastal and littoral areas, and all tourists visiting inland areas enjoy their coastal environments during the visit (going to beaches, consuming coastal-based food and/or undertaking outdoor activities). It is relatively easy to demonstrate that in almost all cases, the iconography and tourism image of the islands are related to the sea and the coastal resources (Bramwell, 2004), and that the main tourist motivations *pull factors* to visit islands rely on sea-based assets (Cameron & Gatewood, 2008).

Another reason is the simplification that this methodological decision implies for the economic valuation and modelling of climate shocks. A different assumption would imply first to estimate which part of the tourism activity that would be affected for changes in environmental services; and then assess the effects of those changes on the total tourism industry.

Under Soclimpact, “Tourism as a demand-side phenomenon refers to the activities of visitors and their role in the acquisition of goods and services, usually related to coastal resources. It can also be viewed from the supply side, and Tourism will then be understood as the set of productive activities catered mainly to visitors during the stay.”

AQUACULTURE

1 NACE is the statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community and is the subject of legislation at the European Union level, which imposes the use of the classification uniformly within all the Member States

Context

“Farming finfish, shellfish and aquatic plants is one of the world's fastest growing food sectors and provides the planet with about half of all the fish we eat”.

The world's population is expected to rise to 9.6 billion by 2050, creating a considerable demand for food and sources of protein, and aquaculture can contribute to assure food security, meet nutrition needs, as well as social and economic inclusion, employment and lessen the need for fish imports in some countries. Sustainable aquaculture is also needed because fisheries alone will not meet the growing demand for seafood (EC, 2015).

In the context of islands, the aquaculture sector needs attention. Although there are hotspots of marine biodiversity because their surrounding near-shore marine areas constitute unique ecosystems, aquaculture has not been developed in its huge potential (World Bank, 2017). Moreover, the ocean that surrounds the islands is of crucial importance as it absorbs vast amounts of CO₂, helping to mitigate human-caused global warming, but causing ocean acidification, which leads to dramatic effects (*e.g.* for calcifying species) on their extraordinarily rich biodiversity. Finally, the diversity of weather and sea conditions in islands leads to very diversified and scenarios production across islands. For example, the stable temperatures in the Atlantic Islands ensure a regular production without seasonality and favour the generation of larger sizes species and ecological certifications but limit the diversity. In other islands (Mediterranean Sea basin for example) weather conditions induce more pathologies but aquaculture production is more heterogeneous.

Definition

Aquaculture is described as the following in the statistical presentation of Eurostat: “Aquaculture, also known as aquafarming, refers to the farming of aquatic (freshwater or saltwater) organisms, such as fish, molluscs, crustaceans and plants, for human use or consumption, under controlled conditions. Aquaculture implies some form of intervention in the natural rearing process to enhance production, including regular stocking, feeding and protection from predators. Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of, or contractual rights to, the stock being cultivated”.

Other very similar definitions can be extracted from the EU Commission document “Aquaculture in the EU: Tapping into Blue Growth”, EU Parliament document “Directorate-General for Internal Policies Structural and Cohesion Policies: Regulatory and Legal Constraints for European Aquaculture” and from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations – FAO.

Soclimpact assumptions

The aquaculture sector will involve only marine-based operations and will exclude freshwater aquaculture, as well as land-based operations (*e.g.* ponds and recirculated aquaculture systems - RAS). Despite the apparent impacts of climate change on terrestrial and freshwater operations, these operations are not common on islands and will not be considered. There will not be boundaries on the proximity of aquaculture sites to the island itself; both offshore and coastal operations will be included. Considering the small size of the aquaculture sector, all marine-based and coastal aquaculture operations will be analysed in the impact chains to collect as much data as possible.

Under Soclimpact, “Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms and is an activity aimed at the production of animal proteins in the aquatic environment, including fish, molluscs,

crustaceans, algae and aquatic plants. Farming implies some form of intervention and control (partial or total, direct or indirect) in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection from predators, *etc.* Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being cultivated.”

According to the Regulation (EC) No 762/2008, the aquaculture production statistics reflect the outputs of the first sale intended for human consumption. Non-commercial aquaculture is rarely accounted for. Moreover, aquaculture production of aquarium and ornamental species and production for industrial, functional or research purposes are also excluded. According to this regulation, data is collected and disseminated yearly in the following tables:

- Aquaculture production at first sale for human consumption (excluding hatcheries and nurseries) by species, by FAO major area, by cultivation method, by aquatic environment (fish_aq2a).
- Production of fish eggs (roe) at first sale for human consumption by species, by FAO major area, by aquatic environment (fish_aq2b).
- Input to capture-based aquaculture, by species (fish_aq3).
- Production of fertilised eggs at first sale for further on-growing or release to the wild by species (fish_aq4a).
- Production of juveniles at first sale for further on-growing or release to the wild by species (fish_aq4b).

MARINE ENERGY

Context

Marine Renewable Energy Sources (RES) have doubled in the last decade and represent approximately 1% of the more than 2 million MW RES installed worldwide capacity (IRENA, 2017). They have the potential to become an important source in the energy mix of coastal regions.

Off-shore wind is the most promising of the technologies, but several energy options are trying to develop and become also cost-competitive alternatives over time, capable of contributing to the exploitation of the energy potentials of our seas and oceans. Besides wind, there is huge clean and renewable energy resources potential in the ocean waves and underwater currents; in the water temperature gradients of tropical regions (Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion - OTEC); in the salinity gradients (still R&D early stage); and in tides (tidal stream technology).

Offshore wind is the fastest growing activity of the blue economy. Wind is steadier at sea than on land, so the average capacity factor is higher and the disturbance to cherished landscapes smaller. As of January 2017, 12,631 MW of capacity was connected to the grid. The EU is a global leader with about 90 % of the newly finished projects in the world. It is estimated that 80% of the EU's wind resource are in waters too deep for traditional fixed turbines. Floating turbines could extend the deployment to deeper waters such as those off the Iberian Atlantic coast or the Mediterranean (IRENA, 2017).

Nevertheless, as the installed marine RES power expands, and as investment cost reductions are achieved, the concern will be shifting towards guaranteeing the safety and reliability of operation of sea power-generation devices and the complementary electrical infrastructure, under severe storms and other negative climate change impacts.

Definition

Renewable energy sources (RES), also called renewables, are energy sources that replenish (or renew) themselves naturally. Typical examples are solar energy, wind and biomass (EC, 2016).

Renewable energy sources include the following:

- Hydropower: the electricity generated from the potential and kinetic energy of water in hydroelectric plants (the electricity generated in pumped storage plants is not included);
- Tide, wave, ocean energy: mechanical energy derived from tidal movement, wave motion or ocean current and exploited for electricity generation;
- Geothermal energy: the energy available as heat from within the earth's crust, usually in the form of hot water or steam;
- Wind energy: the kinetic energy of wind converted into electricity in wind turbines;
- Solar energy: solar thermal energy (radiation exploited for solar heat) and solar photovoltaic for electricity production.

Wave and tidal energy are currently the most mature ocean energy technologies.

Tidal current energy is created by local regular diurnal (24-hour) or semi-diurnal (12+ hour) flows of ocean water caused by the tidal cycle. Kinetic energy can be harnessed, usually nearshore and particularly where there are constrictions, such as straits, islands and passes.

Wave energy is created as kinetic energy from the wind and transmitted to the upper surface of the ocean. At present there are several different wave energy technologies designs, and some are at the cutting edge of engineering design.

Ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC) uses the temperature difference between surface and deep water in a heat cycle to produce electricity. Although tropical areas are most favourable for the exploitation of this source of energy, the potential resources are enormous.

Osmotic power generation exploits the energy available from differences in the salt concentration between seawater and fresh water and is especially suited to countries with abundant fresh water resources flowing into the sea. There are two practical methods for this - reversed electro-dialysis (RED) and pressure retarded osmosis (PRO).

Ocean energy is largely derived from the power of currents, tides and waves and to a lesser extent also from thermal and saline gradients in some locations. The resources are plentiful and the regular nature of their power delivery complements more variable renewable sources such as wind and sun. Estimates suggest that ocean energy could meet 10% of the EU's electricity demand by 2050.

Power generated by the marine RES systems will have to be fed to the island grids. Developing the full potential of marine RES will require heavy investment in electrical infrastructures for connecting off-shore wind farms and other marine RES devices to the island electrical systems.

The energy transition to a more sustainable low carbon energy system, especially in

those islands with a big resident population and high tourist activity, will require developing their specific and more viable marine RES. Also, the application of proper Demand Side Management/Demand Response will contribute to peak shaving of the island electrical demand curve, which combined with energy storage infrastructure, will allow for managing the variability and intermittence of non-dispatchable marine RES generation.

Soclimpact assumptions

Conditions for a future development of marine RES in islands are comparatively better than those exhibited by mainland territories. As technology progresses (floating wind energy platforms, tidal sensitivity devices, *etc.*) islands will take advantage of their diverse conditions alongside their coastlines areas to produce energy.

Secondly, a big part of the energy production, transport and distribution infrastructures are strongly linked to coastal areas. Electric grid goes near to the shoreline, being exposed to marine and coastal climate shocks. Additionally, conventional electric power plants area mostly built at the shoreline precisely to take advantage of the sea proximity as a source for refrigeration and as a sink for wastewaters. Finally, although there are distributed renewable-based electric plants relatively far from the sea line, those are sensitive to extreme climate events, affecting the costs of the blue economy activities of the European islands.

Thirdly, energy is a crucial input for the economic production of islands, while energy shocks, including those linked to climate hazards, will have a great influence, via costs, on the blue economy sectors and hence on the whole islander economies. Additionally, on the demand side, energy uses and/or production features are considered attributes of the tourism products and experiences offered by these destinations, and critical factors to underline them as climate/environmentally friendly. Thus, the energy sector interacts with blue economy activities in islands not only in an intensive way but also from both supply and demand sides.

The strong relation between the energy sector and the blue economy in the islands, and the unlimited borders that blue sectors have in the context of insular economies fully justify the selection of the whole energy sector under the Soclimpact analysis, regardless of the limitations that could arise from the availability and aggregation of data and the functional relations between the marine-based energies and the whole energy systems.

MARITIME TRANSPORT

Context

Europe boasts over 70,000 km of coastline and 27,000 km of navigable inland waterways, and the maritime transport has always been considered a catalyst for its economic development and prosperity, and a source of employment. More than 400 million passengers embark and disembark at European ports every year and 90% of the EU's external freight trade is seaborne (EC, 2017). With 4500 marinas and nautical tourism ports, and 1.75 million of berths, Europe is also a leader destination worldwide for maritime sports and sailing (Cieniewicz, 2014; ICOMIA, 2013).

As by 2050 short sea shipping will have a strong role in reaching the EU transport goal of reducing 60% of greenhouse gas emission generated by transport and by 2030 the shift of 30%

of road freight over 300 km to other modes. To achieve these goals, the design of more effective environmental strategies is required, for which it is crucial to generate more hierarchical and pilot evidences and data about the effects that CC has on the functional activities of this sector (Ecorys, 2017).

Definition

“Maritime transport is the carriage of goods and passengers by sea-going vessels, on voyages undertaken wholly or partly at sea. The data collected from National Statistical Authorities are port statistics: information on goods handled in ports, passengers embarked and disembarked and vessel traffic. Detailed information is collected on the type of cargo and passengers, geographical areas where the partner ports are located, type, size and nationality of ships used to carry out that transportation” (Eurostat, 2017).

The data classification and collection system is based upon the Directive 2009/42/EC and Commission Decision 2008/861/EC, as amended by Commission Decision 2010/216/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of April, 14th 2010, by Regulation 1090/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of November, 24th 2010 and by Commission Delegated Decision 2012/186/EU of February, 3rd 2012 (Eurostat, 2017).

Maritime transport data focuses on three main aspects: i) gross weight of goods (in tons), ii) passenger movements (in number of passengers) and iii) vessel traffic (in number of vessels and in gross tonnage of vessels). The COUNCIL REGULATION (EEC) No 3577/92 of December, 7th 1992 applies to the principle of freedom to provide services to maritime transport within Member States (maritime cabotage). Data is collected by the national competent authorities in the reporting countries using a variety of sources, such as port administration systems, national maritime databases, customs databases or questionnaires to ports or shipping agents.

In the Article 1 of COUNCIL REGULATION (EEC) No 4055 / 86, the following shall be considered “maritime transport services between Member States and between Member States and third countries” where they are normally provided for remuneration:

- (a) intra-Community shipping services: the carriage of passengers or goods by sea between any port of a Member State and any port or off-shore installation of another Member State;
- (b) third-country traffic: the carriage of passengers or goods by sea between the ports of a Member State and ports or off-shore installations of a third country.

Official Journal L 364, 12/12/1992 P. 0007 – 0010

Article 2

For the purposes of this Regulation:

“Maritime transport services within a Member State (maritime cabotage)” shall mean services normally provided for remuneration and shall include:

- (a) *mainland cabotage*: the carriage of passengers or goods by sea between ports situated on the mainland or the main territory of one and the same Member State without calls at islands;
- (b) *off-shore supply services*: the carriage of passengers or goods by sea between any port in a Member State and installations or structures situated on the continental shelf of that Member State;
- (c) *island cabotage*: the carriage of passengers or goods by sea between:

- ports situated on the mainland and on one or more of the islands of one and the same Member State,
- ports situated on the islands of one and the same Member State;

Ceuta and Melilla shall be treated in the same way as island ports.

Soclimpact assumptions

Good maritime transport services ensure a good quality of life on Europe's islands, because islands remain largely dependent on the mainland for supplies and exports. While islands' seaports play a crucial role in the European economy, acting as transportation hubs for most of goods exchange around the world, few evidences and scaled studies have been dedicated to measure the impact that CC has on these specific areas and the policies needed to face them, which is one of the objectives of Soclimpact.

In this attempt, and based on the previous regulations, we assume that the maritime transport sector covers the transport of passengers or cargo by a sea-going vessel between a port of one Party and a port of the other Party or of a third country, or between a port of one Member State of the European Union and a port of another Member State of the European Union, as well as direct contracting with suppliers of other transport services to ensure door-to-door or multimodal transport operations, but not the supply of such other transport services.

2.2. Operational database management and processing

The Soclimpact project brings together different strands of science, such as biology, climate science, hydrology, socio-economics and others. At this early stage of the project, it is relevant to overview the different approaches in data classifications by sector of interest. A fully harmonized system across all sciences and all islands is not - and should not be - sought. However, part of the challenge of this is will be to exceed the classifications and improve the identification of any cross-cutting sector (such as tourism).

The following tries to shed some light on the classification and definitions used in the economic model GINFORS. GINFORS is the global multi-sectoral macro-economic impacts assessment model, which will be used in parallel to the latest version of GEM-E3, a global large scale CGE model to study the impacts of Climate change and mitigation policies. Macro-economic models being the ultimate stage (from WP4 to WP6) in Soclimpact modelling chain, their requirement should influence the modelling activities of WP4 and WP5.

2.2.1. GINFORS: Supply and Use Accounting Framework

The global environmental economics model GINFORS maps interdependent production, trade and use in a *supply* and *use* framework which accounts for the use of 59 categories in 35 industries. The data structure has been adopted from the World Input-Output Database (see <http://www.wiod.org/>), which serves as main historical database of the model. The model contains individual country models for 38 countries (the EU-27 countries, Russia, Turkey, Brazil, Canada, Mexico, the United States, China, India, Japan, Korea and Australia) and a "rest of the world" region. Concerning islands, the national economies of Malta and Cyprus are modelled in

full detail. For other islands, being European regions (NUTS2), an adaptation of the model will be necessary (D6.1).

Industry and goods classifications follow international standards. A complete list of the industry classification can be found in table 2 (rows coded from 1 to 35). NACE codes reported in column two refer to the official NACE rev 1 (ISIC rev 2) classification scheme. Correspondence tables to the NACE rev 2 classification can be inferred from Eurostat correspondence tables. Products and services produced by these industries are classified in accordance with the related CPA 2002 classification. See table 3 for a complete overview (in coherence to the most recent CPA 2008 classification). These products and services are either used as intermediate inputs to individual production processes within the afore mentioned industries or they are used as one of the final demand categories listed up in rows 38 to 45 of table 2.

Table 2: Economic activities mapped by the GINFORS model - Source: Timmer, M. (ed.) (2012): The World Input-Output Database (WIOD): Contents, Sources and Methods. Vers. 0.9.

Code	NACE	Description
1	AtB	Agriculture, Hunting, Forestry and Fishing
2	C	Mining and Quarrying
3	15t16	Food, Beverage and Tobacco
4	17t18	Textiles and textile Products
5	19	Leather, Leather and Footwear
6	20	Wood and Products of Wood and Cork
7	21t22	Pulp, Paper, Printing and Publishing
8	23	Coke, Refined Petroleum and Nuclear Fuel
9	24	Chemical and Chemical Products
10	25	Rubber and Plastics
11	26	Other Non-Metallic Moneral
12	27t28	Basic Metals and Fabricated Metal
13	29	Machinery, Nec
14	30t33	Electrical and Optimal Equipment
15	34t35	Transport Equipment
16	36t37	Manufacturing, Nec; Recycling
17	E	Electricity, Gas and Water Supply
18	F	Construction
19	50	Sale, Maintenance and Repair of Motor Vehicles Retails Sale of Fuel
20	51	Wholesale Trade and Commission Trade, Except of Motor Vehicles
21	52	Retail Trade, Except of Motor Vehicles; Repair of Households Goods
22	H	Hotels and Restaurants
23	60	Inland Transport
24	61	Water Transport
25	62	Air Transport
26	63	Other Supporting and Auxiliary Transport Activities; Travel Agencies
27	64	Post and Telecommunications
28	J	Financial Intermediation
29	70	Real Estate Activities

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30	71t74	Renting of M&Eq and Other Business Activities
31	L	Public Admin and defence; Compulsory Social Security
32	M	Education
33	N	Health and Social Work
34	O	Other Community, Social and Personal Services
35	P	Private Households with Employed Persons
36		Financial Intermediation services indirectly measured (FISIM)
37		Total
38		Final consumption expenditure by households
39		Final consumption exp. By non-profit organisations serving households
40		Final consumption exp. By government
41		Final consumption expenditure
42		Gross fixed capital formation
43		Changes in inventories and valuables
44		Gross capital formation
45		Exports
46		Final uses at purchasers' prices
47		Total use at purchasers' prices

Table 3: Product and service group classification scheme applied in the GINFORS model I/II - Source: Timmer, M. (ed.) (2012): The World Input-Output Database (WIOD): Contents, Sources and Methods. Vers. 0.9.

Code	CPA	Description
1	1	Products of agriculture, hunting and related services
2	2	Products of forestry, logging and related services
3	5	Fish and other fishing products; services incidental of fishing
4	10	Coal and lignite; peat
5	11	Crude petroleum and natural gas; services incidental to oil and gas extraction
6	12	Uranium and thorium ores
7	13	Metal ores
8	14	Other mining and quarrying products
9	15	Food products and beverages
10	16	Tobacco products
11	17	Textiles
12	18	Wearing apparel; furs
13	19	Leather and leather products
14	20	Wood and products of wood and cork (except furniture); articles of straw...
15	21	Pulp, paper and paper products
16	22	Printed matter and recorded media
17	23	Coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuels
18	24	Chemicals, chemical products and man-made fibres
19	25	Rubber and plastic products
20	26	Other non-metallic mineral products
21	27	Basic metals
22	28	Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
23	29	Machinery and equipment n.e.c.
24	30	Office machinery and computers
25	31	Electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.
26	32	Radio, television and communication equipment and apparatus
27	33	Medical, precision and optical instruments, watches and clocks
28	34	Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
29	35	Other transport equipment
30	36	Furniture; other manufactured goods n.e.c.
31	37	Secondary raw materials
32	40	Electrical energy, gas, steam, and hot water
33	41	Collected and purified water, distribution services of water
34	45	Construction work
35	50	Trade, maintenance and repair services of motor vehicles and motorcycles...

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36	51	Wholesale trade and commission trade services, except motor vehicles..
37	52	Retail trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair..
38	55	Hotel and restaurant services
39	60	Land transport, transport via pipeline services
40	61	Water transport services
41	62	Air transport services
42	63	Supporting and auxiliary transport services; travel agency services
43	64	Post and telecommunication services
44	65	Financial intermediation services, except insurance and pension funding
45	66	Insurance and pension funding services; except compulsory social security
46	67	Services auxiliary to financial intermediation
47	70	Real estate services
48	71	Renting services of machinery and equipment...
49	72	Computer and related services
50	73	Research and development services
51	74	Other business services
52	75	Public administration and defence services...
53	80	Education services
54	85	Health and social work services
55	90	Sewage and refuse disposal services; sanitation and similar services
56	91	Membership organisation services n.e.c.
57	92	Recreational, cultural, and sporting services
58	93	Other services
59	95	Private households with employed persons
60		Total
61		Cif/fob adjustments on exports
62		Direct purchases abroad by residents
63		Purchases on the domestic territory by non-residents
64		Total intermediate consumption/final use at purchasers' prices
65		Compensation of employees
66		Other net taxes on production
67		Operating surplus, gross
68		Value added at basic prices
69		Output at basic prices

GINFORS is commonly labelled as a macro-econometric model. This label refers to the fact that the economic dynamics of all behavioural equations as well as of industrial input output structures are estimated by time series regression analyses of historical observations. To model climate damages within the Soclimpact project, therefore, almost all these functions may be altered between individual scenario simulations. This enables, for example, to simulate the impacts of declining consumer propensities to spend money on hotel and restaurant services in the selected regions.

It is important to note that, apart from these predefined simulations starting points, we will also explore the potentials to extend our usual mapping scheme (at least for selected islands and sectors) within a task in the WP6 of the Soclimpact project. Ideally, these activities will be advanced in a close exchange with respective sector leads and island focal points on a continuing basis.

2.2.2. Enhancing GINFORS sectors coverage

Currently, GINFORS covers aquaculture activities implicitly within the broader economic aggregate “Agriculture, Hunting, Forestry and Fishing”. However, as a matter of principle this modelling pattern might be refined by the inclusion of further detailed time series observations in the historical database. Basically, this task would demand for a thorough statistical breakdown of the aquaculture activities in the geographical region under inspection. As earlier work on “Green Jobs, Green Economy” shows, it is often required to provide estimates about the input structure of a green – or blue – sector. Data analysis will require time series data.

As indicated (table 4), historical time series for NACE Rev. 2 group 03.2 (Aquaculture) could suffice for a refined modelling of aquaculture activities. The historical dynamics of this NACE groups would then have to be transferred to the usual mapping of intermediate and final demand flows in GINFORS. This will certainly require the involvement of some strong technical working hypotheses. Yet, given sufficient historical time series observations (which should ideally also report about labour inputs as well as price and wage dynamics in the respective NACE groups) such approach might basically be implemented.

Table 4: Example of Fishing, statistical subgroups according to NACE classification - Source: NACE Rev. 2. Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2008.

n.e.c not elsewhere classified				*part of
Division	Group	Class		ISIC Rev 4
03	<i>Fishing and aquaculture</i>			
	<i>03.1</i>		<i>Fishing</i>	
		03.11	Marine fishing	0311
		03.12	Freshwater fishing	0312
	<i>03.2</i>		<i>Aquaculture</i>	
		03.21	Marine aquaculture	0321
		03.22	Freshwater aquaculture	0322

Maritime Transport refers to those economic activities labelled “Water Transport” in GINFORS. The related outputs contribute to the service group “Water transport services”. Nevertheless, it would be highly welcome if the statistical information provided by island focal points partners could cover the whole set of official NACE groups enumerated within the table 5. Again, as a basic

principle, we would require historical time series observations (preferably also reporting about labour inputs as well as price and wage dynamics in respective NACE groups).

Table 5: Water transport, statistical subgroups according to NACE - Source: NACE Rev. 2. Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2008.

n.e.c not elsewhere classified				*part of
Division	Group	Class		ISIC Rev 4
50	Water transport			
	50.1	<i>Sea and coastal passenger water transport</i>		
		50.10	Sea and coastal passenger water transport	5011
	50.2	<i>Sea and coastal freight water transport</i>		
		50.20	Sea and coastal freight water transport	5012
	50.3	<i>Inland passenger water transport</i>		
		50.30	Inland passenger water transport	5013
	50.4	<i>Inland freight water transport</i>		
	50.40	Inland freight water transport	5014	

The energy module of GINFORS projects for each mapped national economy the following:

1. energy demand (differentiated for 20 energy carriers) by individual industries and private households,
2. the evolution of the energy carrier mix in electricity production subject to key scenario parameters (nuclear energy, total share of renewables),
3. resulting CO2-emissions.

As indicated by bullet point 1, the mapping of economy-wide industrial and private energy demand distinguishes 20 energy carriers. Table 6 shows a complete overview of this classification.

Table 6: Industrial and private energy demand: List of energy carriers

No	Carrier
1	Hard coal and derivatives
2	Lignite and derivatives
3	Coke
4	Crude oil, NGL and feedstocks
5	Diesel oil for road transport
6	Motor gasoline
7	Jet fuel (kerosene and gasoline)
8	Light Fuel oil
9	Heavy fuel oil
10	Naphta
11	Other petroleum products
12	Natural gas

13	Derived gas
14	Industrial and municipal waste
15	Biogasoline also including hydrated ethanol
16	Biodiesel
17	Other combustible renewables
18	Electricity
19	Heat
20	Electricity for e-mobility

Bullet point 2 refers to the modelling of intermediate inputs of the sector “Electricity, Gas and Water Supply”. Table 7 provides an overview of the applied classification of energy carriers. Akin to the previously indicated refinement possibilities with regards to currently applied sector mappings, energy-related model structures might eventually also be further developed.

Table 7: Electricity and heat production: List of energy carriers

No	Carrier
1	Biogas
2	Hydroelectric
3	Geothermal
4	Photovoltaic
5	Solar thermal heat
6	Solar thermal electricity
7	Wind power
8	Nuclear
9	Coal
10	Gas
11	Oil

Unlike the afore-mentioned industries (which are well-identified with their output by the official statistical classification schemes), the tourism industry is defined primarily from demand (by visitor) and is not measured as a sector of national accounts. Thus, the statistical identification of tourism-related economic activities constitutes a cross-cutting accounting exercise². Over the past two decades several countries and international organizations became increasingly aware of respective statistical information deficits. The basic procedure for measuring the size of specific economic activities by functions in theme-specific economic accounts – so-called satellite accounts – is drafted in the current System of National Accounts (2008). The corresponding manuals, Recommended Methodological Framework (2008) and International Recommendations for Tourism Statistics (2010) are the most important source for studying the conceptual features of

² Tourism is of course directly related to the activities “Hotels and Restaurants”, “Inland Transport”, “Water Transport”, “Air Transport” and “Other Supporting and Auxiliary Transport Activities”. However, the task of mapping the overall economic effects of tourism is very complex as the complex interrelationships of an amalgam of industries (spreading out to further services like food and beverage services or recreation activities) must be represented.

tourism satellite accounts (TSAs)³. The TSA framework facilitates systematic measurement of the direct economic impact of tourism activities. GWS is well-experienced in applications of TSA frameworks⁴. Thus, the establishment of individual TSA approaches within GINFORS might generally be considered as an option. However, such an approach is certainly very data demanding. The “maritime and coastal tourism” sector is not included as a sector in economic models, it has several crosscutting sectors such as restauration or accommodation: the boundaries should be defined to include those satellite accounts.

2.2.3. GEM-E3 sectoral disaggregation

The current version of GEM-E3 Computable General Equilibrium model has been calibrated to the latest statistics (GTAP 9, IEA, UN, ILO) while Eurostat statistics have been included instead of the GTAP IO tables for the EU Member States. The GTAP data base includes detailed consumption, production and bilateral trade for 57 commodities⁵ and provides harmonized Social Accounting Matrices across all 140 regions that it covers. For the specific purposes of the analyses conducted by GEM-E3 model, specific GTAP sectors have been aggregated in one single GEM-E3 sector, while other GTAP sectors have been split so to serve a detailed disaggregation of commodities which is particularly relevant of specific applications. GEM-E3 currently features a rich sectoral detail, with 39 categories of economic activities (Table 8), containing a separate representation of the sectors that produce low-carbon power supply technologies, electric cars and advanced appliances. In addition to the above sectors, the model features a detailed representation of the power generation system with 10 different power technologies, along with a very detailed transport supply module (private and public transport modes).

Table 8: GEM-E3 economic activities – current state

GEM-E3 economic activities			
1	Agriculture		
	Wheat, Cereal Grains, Sugar cane, sugar		
2	beet	29	Construction
3	Oil Seeds	30	Business services and R&D
4	Forestry	31	Market Services
5	Coal	32	Non Market Services
6	Crude Oil	33	Air transport
7	Oil	34	Road -Passenger transport
8	Gas Extraction	35	Water - Freight transport
9	Gas	36	Road-Freight transport
10	Power Supply	37	Rail -Freight transport
11	Biomass Solid	38	Rail -Passenger transport
12	Ethanol	39	Water - Passenger transport

³ UNSD/Eurostat/OECD/UNWTO (2008). 2008 Tourism Satellite Account: Recommended Methodological Framework (TSA: RMF 2008).

UNWTO (2010). International Recommendations for Tourism Statistics 2008. New York: United Nations Department of Economic and Statistical Affairs.

⁴ Ahlert, G. (2007). Methodological aspects of preparing the German TSA, empirical findings and initial reactions. Tourism Economics, 13(2), pp. 275-287.

⁵ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/contribute/detailedsector.asp>

13	Bio-diesel	40	Coal fired
14	Ferrous metals	41	Oil fired
15	Non-ferrous metals	42	Gas fired
16	Chemical Products	43	Nuclear
17	Paper Products	44	Biomass
18	Non-metallic minerals	45	Hydro
19	Electronic Goods	46	Wind
20	Conventional Transport equipment	47	PV
21	Other Equipment Goods	48	CCS coal
22	Consumer Goods Industries	49	CCS Gas
23	Advanced Electric Appliances	50	Other power supply
24	Equipment for wind power technology		
25	Equipment for PV panels		
26	Equipment for CCS power technology		
	Other Advanced Heating and Cooking		
27	Appliances		
28	Electric Vehicles		

Macroeconomic models like the GEM-E3 model have been widely used for the purposes of applied, evidence-based, quantified assessments of policies and environmental tensions. In the sections below, a first description of the incorporation of Blue growth sectors in GEM-E3 model is provided, with a focus on the operational definition of the respective sectors. A further description of the methodology that is followed to incorporate these sectors will follow in subsequent Soclimpact reports, those related to WP6.

For consistency purposes across all research teams within Soclimpact project, the NACE Rev.2 specification is chosen as a common statistical classification where applicable. GTAP provides the concordances between the GTAP sectors and the UN ISIC and CPC classifications⁶, thus through the correspondence table⁷ between ISIC Rev.4 and NACE Rev.2 we can derive the correspondence of GEM-E3 sectors to NACE Rev.2 classification.

Marine energy

GEM-E3 model features a detailed bottom-up power supply module with 10 explicit power supply technologies. Like the inclusion of the abovementioned 10 power technologies, GEM-E3 will also incorporate ocean energy for the purposes of Soclimpact project. In the current GEM-E3 version, offshore wind is included in the “wind” sector while wave and tidal energy is included in the “other power supply” sector, both of which will be split for the better representation of ocean energy in GEM-E3.

Coastal and maritime tourism

Tourism is not measured in national accounts as a single separate economic sector but rather comprises several economic activities. These respective economic activities are endogenously simulated in GEM-E3, thus by assuming specific country-specific coefficients, the economic activity of the tourism sector can be assessed with GEM-E3 model. This approach takes stock of

⁶ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/statcom/doc02/isic.pdf>

⁷ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/cr/registry/regso.asp?Ci=70>

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the supply side perspective and the Recommended Methodological Framework of the Tourism Satellite Accounts. A methodology will be derived in WP6 to decompose the relevant GEM-E3 sectors to the respective tourism-related NACE activities (see table 2).

Maritime transport

Maritime transport is a key economic activity that supports all other activities that take place on the islands, providing the necessary linkages to other geographical areas, the ability for the islands to trade and the access to tourists. GEM-E3 model already has an explicit representation of maritime transport, distinguishing freight and passenger purposes, corresponding to NACE codes 50.1 to 50.4.

Aquaculture

Aquaculture is currently included in the aggregate Agriculture sector of GEM-E3. GTAP database however includes a separate sector for fishing, which includes all types of fishing activities namely hunting, trapping, fishing, fish farms, and service activities incidental to fishing. Depending on data availability, the aggregate economic sector of agriculture could be disaggregated to “fishing” and “rest of agriculture” but a further decomposition to fishing and aquaculture (fish farms) would still be required. This disaggregation effort is subject to data availability and subject to the economic size of the aquaculture sector to the total economy.

2.3. Synthesis

The following definitions summarize the 4 blue economy sectors studied in Soclimpact:

From the Soclimpact project perspective, climate change events affect tourism through both supply-side and demand-side. Broken infrastructures due to sea level rise and changes in wave characteristics, degraded coastal environments or the costs of work needed to avoid them, affect the way (costs) in which tourism is produced (supply-side). Loss beach areas, loss of attractiveness or diminished climate comfort affect the expenditure and choice of tourists concerning destinations (demand-side). Tourism as a demand-side phenomenon refers to the activities of visitors and their role in the acquisition of goods and services. It can also be viewed from the supply side, and tourism will then be understood as the set of productive activities that cater mainly to visitors.

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms and is an activity aimed at the production of animal proteins in the aquatic environment, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans, algae and aquatic plants. Aquaculture takes place in both marine and inland areas. Farming implies some form of intervention and control (partial or total, direct or indirect) in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection from predators, *etc.* Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being cultivated.

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Major island electrical infrastructure needed to feed power generated by marine energy systems, which includes substations, high voltage transmission and distribution grids, conventional fossil back-up power stations, energy storage systems, are physically located within the defined coastal area. In an island context, especially for non-interconnected islands, there are other more technical arguments for including also land energy infrastructure in the marine energy analysis. There is a difference between marine electricity, and other marine products obtained from other blue economy related activities, such as aquaculture, marine biotechnology or seabed mining. Electricity generation from marine RES systems installed in island surrounding waters, is not a commodity that could be stored, transported over long distances, and sold in overseas markets, but is energy that must be fed to the island electrical grid, and consumed in the island. Marine RES power generation from the supply-side must be balanced at every instant of time with demand-side electricity consumption of the island. This grid balancing in the island context is an important technical challenge for non-interconnected island electrical systems, especially in high RES penetration scenarios. The forms of ocean energy are waves, tides, marine currents, salinity gradient and temperature gradient. Wave and tidal energy are currently the most mature technologies.

International maritime transport services mean the transport of passengers or cargo by a sea-going vessel between a port of one Party and a port of the other Party or of a third country, or between a port of one Member State of the European Union and a port of another Member State of the European Union, as well as direct contracting with suppliers of other transport services to ensure door-to-door or multimodal transport operations, but not the supply of such other transport services.

3. Selection of priority impacts

In this phase of the project, a first inventory of the priority climate change impacts for each sector was produced. This will serve as a basis for the design of impact chains, which is the next deliverable. Within the consortium, *Sector leads*, i.e. partners identified for their sectoral perspective, undertook this impact identifications in each sector, based on literature review and stakeholders' consultation. These partners were AquaBioTech for aquaculture, Instituto Tecnico de Canarias for Energy, CETECIMA for Maritime Transport, and ULPGC and TEC for Tourism.

From this initial list of impacts, some Impact chains were developed, then presented to stakeholders in 12 Local working groups (1 per island), confronted to a first feasibility analysis in term of modelling resources and data needs. This led:

- to a list of 17 impact chains (presented in D.3.2) common to all islands;

- to a hierarchisation of priority impact chains to be fully operationalised using the indicator approach. 7 Impact chains were selected (3 for tourism, 1 for aquaculture, 1 for maritime transport, 2 for energy).

Soclimpact mostly selected *negative* consequences of climate change, probably for a more urgent action. It must be noted however, that the impacts of climate change can be either *positive* or *negative*. This is particularly true for the tourism sector: the evolution of climate parameters could render the climate more attractive, notably in shoulder seasons (Spring- Autumn). Figure 1 show for instance some projections of the “Beach climate index” an index illustrating the climate suitability for seaside tourism (swimming, etc.), with a general improvement of climate conditions for 2071-2100, even in summer.

Positive impacts must also be highlighted: they require an adaptation, i.e. adopting actions allowing to harvest their potential (developing an off-peak tourism supply...).

Figure 1. Change in the number of days where BCI>70 (right plot) for the 2071-2100 and the 1971-2000 periods using the KNMI model with the A1B emissions scenario. Figures are for Cyprus.

3.1. Towards impact chain

The selection of priority impacts must be done having in mind the project ambition, which is to *measure*, to *estimate* the climate risks for islands. This will require to develop systemic diagrams (see also D3.2), articulating the component of risks:

- Hazard, defined as the **potential occurrence** of a **climate-related physical event or trends** or their **physical impacts** that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts, as well as damage and loss to property, infrastructure, livelihoods, service provision, ecosystems, and environmental resources;

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- Exposure, expressed as the **presence** of people, livelihoods, species or ecosystems, environmental functions, services, and resources, infrastructure, or economic, social, or cultural assets in places and settings that could be adversely affected;
- Vulnerability, which is the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Vulnerability encompasses a variety of concepts and elements including **sensitivity** or **susceptibility to harm** and **lack of capacity to cope and adapt**;
- Impacts, being an intermediate component, i.e. the **effects on natural and human systems** : effects on lives, livelihoods, health, ecosystems, economies, societies, cultures, services, and infrastructure due to the **interaction of climate changes or hazardous climate events** occurring within a specific time period and the **vulnerability** of an **exposed society or system**.

This terminology will guide the rest of the project, and serve as a mean of interdisciplinary dialogue. Several training sessions were organised to train project participants to this common concept of climate risks, and to the definition of impact chains.

Moreover, one should insist on the systemic and dynamic nature of Impact chains:

- SOCLIMPACT will try, as far as possible, to develop and test an approach to assess CC risks that covers both the short-term need of **adjusting in the current societal framework** and the possible need for long-term and large-scale efforts of **societal transformation**. The latter relates to “(t)he altering of fundamental attributes of a system (including value systems; regulatory, legislative, or bureaucratic regimes; financial institutions; and technological or biological systems)” (IPCC, 2012). In practice, several socio-economic scenarios, as provided by WP6, will serve as input for exposure and vulnerability indicators, so that the climate be not the only factor to evolve.
- The knowledge of climate risks must then be co-produced with stakeholders. CC adaptation requires a rigorous and shared scientific knowledge base which must be translated to local practical and actionable knowledge on climate risks and adaptation options. Therefore, a constructive dialogue between researchers and stakeholders is at the core of this project. Exchange of information through joint reflection and learning, e.g. co-exploration and co-production exercises, facilitates joint understanding and awareness, which ultimately shapes knowledge development, influences decisions and shapes behavior. Thus Soclimpact will refine a structured method of **co-production of knowledge**, and integrate this into impact modelling to better account for different views on desirable and equitable climate resilient futures. This is the objective of Island Focal Points and associated Local working groups, established to improve the participation of stakeholders.

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Figure 2: Impact chains and the IPCC AR5 concept of risks

3.2. Maritime and coastal tourism

Climate is a key resource for tourism and has diverse functions in tourism (Day, Chin, Sydnor & Cherkauer, 2013). It can be considered i) a geophysical resource (Martín, 1999) with high capacity to generate competitive advantages for the destinations (Ritchie & Crouch, 2003), ii) an intangible component of the attractiveness and the image of destinations (Moreno, Beerli & De León, 2012), and the set of experiences they offer (Day *et al.*, 2013), and iii) a resource frequently used for tourism promotion (De Freitas *et al.*, 2008; Hamilton & Lau, 2005).

Also, tourism activity is highly sensitive to the impacts of climate change. That is why the analysis of the relationships between climate and tourism has been presented as an important research challenge in recent years (Denstadli & Jacobsen, 2014). Thus, research suggests that climate change, as well as the perceptions of climate comfort risk of tourists (Gössling *et al.*, 2006), are modifying the preferences of tourism demand (Araña, León, Moreno-Gil & Zubiaurre, 2013). Similarly, these perceptions can generate important changes in the geography of tourism at a global level (Yu, Schwartz & Walsh, 2009). The available studies do not allow for a full understanding of these changes and the climate and tourism policies needed to deal with them (Gössling *et al.*, 2006; Scott, Hall & Stefan, 2012).

Adopting an efficient and successful strategy of adaptation and mitigation requires an accurate identification and valuation of the climate change impacts on tourism and of the corresponding necessary policies. As tourism and climate are related in many ways, it is crucial to develop a common methodological framework to evaluate climate shocks and policy impacts (table 9).

Table 9: Climate change impacts and implications for tourism in the European islands

Hazard (trends and extreme events)	Biophysical and physical impacts (positive or negative)	Socio economic impacts
Air temperature rise	- Changes in plant-wildlife-insect populations and distribution	- Heat stress for tourists affecting comfort, demand and receipts

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Larger range of infectious disease - Altered seasonality - Better tourism conditions in shoulder seasons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased cooling costs for tourism facilities - Stress on the electric supply network
Sea temperature rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased coral bleaching with degradation of biodiversity and sea landscapes - Seagrass deterioration with loss of ecosystem services, coastal protection and sediment retention. - Arrival of exotic species - Improved swimming conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Loss of attractive in sea landscape-based destinations (dive, snorkel, bottom-glass ships, <i>etc.</i>)
Sea level rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased coastal erosion and /or flood of sand beaches - Salinization of coastal underground water reservoirs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Loss of beach area negatively influencing tourism demand. - Higher maintenance costs for tourist facilities to protect and maintain waterfronts
Increased droughts due to reduced rainfall and increased evapotranspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Degradation of natural habitats - Increased erosion and desertification - Increased wildfires. - Lesser water availability for human uses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water shortage and overpricing. - Landscape degradation and sightseeing devaluation affecting demand. - Increased costs of operations in tourism facilities caused by loss of local food supply for tourism.
Increased frequency and intensity of extreme climate events (storms, flooding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in coastal sedimentary processes. - Beaches degradation due to inland waste and materials depositions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Business interruption costs. - Demand decrease due to risks. - Damages to tourism facilities, historic assets, beaches and infrastructure increasing costs of maintenance and insurance.

3.3. Marine energy

The impacts on marine energy are related with:

- Different population densities
- Different seasonal variation in tourist activities

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- Different dependence on fishery and aquaculture activities
- Different past successful stories promoting Green energy (on-land RES), or paradigmatic Circular economy experiences (successfully implementing 3R waste management: Reduce, Reuse, Recycle).
- Different geographical areas/different countries: One Atlantic island (to choose from Madeira, Gran Canarias or an island in Azores); three Mediterranean islands (to choose from Cyprus, Malta, Crete, Corsica, Majorca, Sardinia or Sicily).

Table 10: Climate change impacts for marine energy in the European islands

Hazard (Trends and extreme events)	Biophysical impacts (positive or negative)	Socio economic impacts
Increased frequency and intensity of extreme climate events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Damage to marine RES energy generation system - Damage to associated electrical infrastructure: transmission and distribution grid; energy storage (off-shore and marine energy systems require expensive infrastructure) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase cost of maintenance, insurance and adaptation actions to increase resilience and reduce vulnerability of energy infrastructures
Air temperature rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased need for more power generation installed - Transmission and substation capacities reduced. - Gas-turbine power plant generation efficiency reduction - Diminution of heating needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stressed energy demand by demand rising for electricity - Higher energy demand for cooling and water production (sea and brackish water desalination) - Diminution of energy demand and bill
Sea level rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased risk for electrical substations and possibly for other electrical coastal infrastructures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased costs for design and implementation of measures/policies to reduce the vulnerability of energy infrastructure to flooding
Increased droughts due to reduced rainfall and increased evapotranspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased needs to install reverse osmosis seawater desalination plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased costs of seawater reverse osmosis desalination for covering water needs.

Greenhouse effects (concentration of CO ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase corrosion damage due to increase in atmospheric CO₂, and carbon induced corrosion, is a major cause of reinforcement corrosion in concrete infrastructures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased maintenance costs for infrastructures
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in ocean acidity can increase corrosion of marine exposed infrastructures 	

3.4. Maritime Transport

The impacts identified are related mainly with the ports and their infrastructures (table 11). They could be applied to all European islands.

Table 11: Climate change impacts for maritime transport in the European islands

Hazard (Trends and extreme events)	Biophysical impacts (positive or negative)	Socio economic impact
Sea level rise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Floods on ports. - Damage to storage capacity. - Damage in ports' infrastructures and equipment's (navigation). - Increase in the number of operational stops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased users' risk perception leading to lower rates of moorings and turnover. - Increased costs of maintenance in nautical installations and equipment's
Increased frequency and intensity of extreme climate events (storms, flooding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Damage to storage capacity. - Damage in ports' infrastructures and equipment's (navigation). - Increase in the number of operational stops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased costs for new investment and insurance - Carbon tax affects fossil fuel prices. - Less turnover from maritime transport activities. - Disruption costs

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3.5. Aquaculture

The impacts identified so far are applicable to marine aquaculture in all European islands (table 15).

Table 12: Climate change impacts for aquaculture in the European islands

Hazard (Trends or extreme events)	Physical impacts (positive or negative)	Socio economic impact
Temperature changes of sea water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase harmful algal blooms - Decreased oxygen level - Increase in diseases and parasites - Changes in ranges of suitable species - Increased growth rate - Increased Food Conversion ratio - Longer growing season 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in production levels (decrease or increase in production) - -Increase in fouling and pests
Changes in currents and waves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -Decreased flushing rates (shell fish) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - Accumulation of waste under cages
Increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher waves and storm surges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stock loss - Damage to facility/structure - Need to invest in stronger constructions - Higher insurance costs - -Changes in suitability of sites

4. Validated Matrix on Blue Economy

Soclimpact requires an adapted governance, allowing working:

- at a sector level;
- at an island level;
- at a WP level, in a quite disciplinary perspective;
- at an interdisciplinary level, around the concept of risk assessment.

The WP3 workshop organized in Rome, October 10-12th 2018, officialized a need to rethink the “scientific governance” of the project during its second year, to be able to deliver more efficiently. Several roles were confirmed our initiates.

4.1. Island focal points

At island level, the project needs

- to link with stakeholders, to bridge climate risk assessment and adaptation planning;

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- to collect the data needed for climate risk and economic modelling, and not available at the European level.

Some Soclimpact partners clearly have a territorial focus (e.g. ANCI Sardinia, the association of local authorities in Sardinia), or are more boundary organisations (e.g. OTIE, working on tourism and islands in general, but based in Sardinia).

Therefore, the 1st amendment to the Grant agreement introduced this role of Island Focal Point, in charge of

- Facilitate meetings between Soclimpact partners and local stakeholders : creation of a local working groups
- Find specific contacts in the various studied sectors in island
- Identify local data sources upon request
- Help identifying case studies
- Will further integrate Wps results in « Island reports »

List of Island Focal points

Island	Island Focal Point
Azores	FCIENCIAS.ID
Balearic Islands	UIB
Baltic Islands	BEF Germany
Canary Islands	ULPGC
Corsica	TEC
Crete	E3M
Cyprus	INTERFUSION
Madeira	AREAM
Malta	ABT
Sardegna	ANCI
Sicilia	OTIE
West Indies	UA

Calendar of Local Working Group Meetings

Date	May	June	July	September					October		December	
	17th	22th	16th	10th	20th	20th	24th/27th	25th	27th	2nd	3rd	17th
Island	Corsica	Sicily	Crete	Baltic Islands	Sardegna	Malta	Madeira / Azores	West Indies (Guadalupe & ...)		Canary Islands	Cyprus	Balearic Islands
IFP organizing	TEC	OTIE	KRITI	BEF	ANCI	ABT	AREAM/FcienciasID	UA		ULPGC	CYI	UIB
Presence of POT member	Matias, Carmelo, Lucie (ULPGC)	Elodie (TEC)	None, but Zoi (E3M) as a support	None	Yen (ULPGC)	None	Elodie (TEC)	Lucie (ULPGC)		ITC & CETECIMA partners as support	None	None

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4.2. Sector leaders

During the 1st year of the project, some *Sector leads*, i.e. partners identified for their sectoral expertise, undertook this impact identifications in each sector, based on literature review and stakeholders' consultation. They also drafted the 1st versions of Impact chains. These partners were AquaBioTech for aquaculture, Instituto Tecnico de Canarias for Energy, CETECIMA for Maritime Transport, and ULPGC and TEC for Tourism.

4.3. Sector modelling teams

The project is organized around WPs, while the work is organized around Impact Chains (and will still be during the rest of the project). Therefore, we need to keep on working at the sector level, in parallel to the WP level. Thus the proposal was to create, for year 2 and 3 of the project, 4 "Sectoral modelling teams- SMT" (Tourism, Maritime Transport, Aquaculture, Energy).

Mandate

- 1st meeting (physical or online) to discuss data needs (based on indicator of D3.3 and modeling chain 3.4), modelling strategy, normalization and weighting challenges and desired outputs
- *WP4, WP5 and WP6 members report to their WP, to discuss capacity to handle request, allocate resources and priorities inside WP4, 5 and 6*
- 2nd meeting: first attempt to assemble the ICs, make the normalization and weighting, compute the first scores, test robustness, etc.
- *WP4, WP5 and WP6 members report to their WP, to discuss capacity to handle requests, allocate resources and priorities inside WP4 and 6*
- 3rd meeting : to refine the choices and prepare final computation
- 4th meeting : discussing results and prepare reporting

Procedure

- Call for participants in each sector group, based on first interests expressed in GA1 (Canarias) and WP3 workshop (Corsica)
- Typical composition : one representant of WP4, one WP5, one of WP6, the sector leader, and all other partners interested
- Proposals of chair and co-chair of this group.
- At each GA some time is devoted to these sectoral modelling groups, with physical or on-line meetings in between.

WP3 will facilitate this process, providing templates and participating to sector groups (to ensure for instance a consistent approach of ICs).

4.4. Task force on Normalisation, Weighting and Aggregation

It was decided to establish an informal Task force on “Normalisation, Weighing, Aggregation and Visualisation of Impact chains”, to provide internal guidance for this topic, in particular on the key issue of articulating modelling and normalization/ aggregation

Mandate

The impact chain approach requires normalization of all parts of it, because the resulting risk is a weighted result of hazards, vulnerabilities, exposure and socio-economic impacts. The informal task force will develop internal guidelines on this aggregation. It will not do the aggregation itself, but point at possible flaws of aggregation and additions.

The Task force has more precisely 2 objectives :

1. How to operationalize the ICs (= how to end with a quantified value of climate risk ?)
2. How to transfer the results to stakeholders (visualisation, reporting...)

Composition

The composition of the task force involved the following researchers from the consortium (selected for their knowledge of climate risk assessment and their capacity to elaborate quantitative analysis):

- Piero Ionello (CMCCC)
- Valentina Bacciu (CMCC)
- Matthias Hernandez (ULPGCC)
- Gabriel Jorda (UIB)
- Ghislain Dubois (TEC- Ramboll)
- Elodie Briche (TEC-Ramboll)
- Cristos Gianakoulos (NOA)

The Task force met on-line at 6 occasions (presentation and minutes in the Dropbox)

- 19.11.2018: Setting up objectives and clarifying concepts
- 10.12.2018: Initial methods for the normalization, weighting and aggregation of indicators
- 01.02.2019 : Proposition of targeted visualization
- 19.02.2019 : Developmeng of a test case on current and future forest fires in islands
- 21.03.2019 : Meeting of the Impact chain on forest fire sub-group
- 16.04.2019 : Normalization, discretization and weighting using the MCA-AHP method; first results for islands
- 11.06.2019: Meeting of the Impact chain on forest fire sub-group

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4.5. Responsibilities during the 1st year of the project

This part is a synthesis of the governance of the WP3 and implications of the 24 partners in the 12 islands, during the 1st year of the project. The IFP is the head of the Local Working Group (1 LWG per island) and the direct contact point between external islands stakeholders and project partners. The IFPs work with islands stakeholders, which compose the LWG in the following ways:

- Collect feedback concerning their interest in specific information of the project, according to their field and scope of action;
- Explain the datasets required for the project, ask how they could participate in providing data and what would be their interest in doing so;
- Present some of the deliverables to and validate them at regional scale, according to their usefulness for policy implementation;
- Identify channels of information more attractive and accessible for them: these identified channels of information should then go into the dissemination plan.

The sector leaders are project partners who have a specific expertise in the below-mentioned domains. Sector teams have also been created and those teams intervene when in-depth sector knowledge is needed for the research.

Table 13 summarizes the partners acting as sector leaders, IFPs and the rest of partners that can intervene to support the empirical application of the project to the islands case study.

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Table 13: Matrix sectors/islands interests

FOCAL POINTS ----- Sectors leaders	Azore / FCIENCIAS.ID	Balearic Islands / UIB	Fehmarn/BE F	Canary Islands/ ULPGC	Corsica / TEC	Crete/ E3M	Cyprus/ INTERFUSION	Madeira/AREAM	Malta/ ABT	Sardegna / ANCI	Sicilia/ OTIE	West Indies / UA
Maritime transport CETECIMA	FCiencias.ID	UIB	BEF	CETECIMA	TEC		E3M	AREAM	E3M		OTIE	UA
Coastal and maritime tourism ULPGC	FCiencias.ID UCLM/ TEC	UIB UCLM/ NOA	BEF	CETECIMA / ULPGC UCLM	UCLM/ TEC/ NOA	UCLM / TEC/ NOA	E3M/ Interfusion UCLM/ TEC/ NOA	AREAM UCLM	E3M UCLM / NOA	UCLM/ TEC/ NOA	UCLM / NOA/ OTIE	TEC/ UA
Aquaculture ABT	FCiencias.ID	UIB		CETECIMA	TEC			AREAM	ABT		OTIE	UA
Marine energy ITC	FCiencias.ID	UIB/ UCLM	-	ITC/ UCLM	TEC		CYI	AREAM			OTIE	

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5. Conclusion

This first deliverable makes it possible to lay the foundations and bases and more especially the framework of the Soclimpact project in terms of sectoral definitions and boundaries and of sectoral brainstorming.

These definitions are not intended to be exhaustive but to take into consideration the boundaries of the four sectors selected in Soclimpact, adapted to the specificities of the partners (which explains the change for the aquaculture sector) and the islands represented within the project. These definitions are based on European regulations and documents recognized by the leading sectors as most relevant for the definition within the project dealing with island areas in different climate zones.

Scientific research concerning the criteria for selecting pilot sites and impact chains according to spatial and temporal scales of studies will be analysed in detail in the next deliverables.

In addition, the philosophy of the Soclimpact project, which is based on a very strong interrelation between the working groups (the outputs of one WP are the inputs of the next one) plays a leading role in the choice of definitions. They must consider the future modelling phases of WP4, 5 and 6. For the moment, the aim was to carry out an inventory of the definitions of these sectors within the Soclimpact models to avoid any error in relation to the European legislation and statistics in force; nevertheless, these aspects of interrelation will be dug in the various work packages.

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